

A Lightweight Software Stack for IoT Interoperability within the Computing Continuum

Dimitrios Spatharakis*, Ioannis Dimolitsas*, Giacomo Genovese[†], Ioannis Tzanettis*, Nikos Filinis*, Eleni Fotopoulou*, Constantinos Vassilakis*, Anastasios Zafeiropoulos*, Antonio Iera[‡], Antonella Molinaro[†], Symeon Papavassiliou*

*School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Greece

[†]Dept. DIIES, University Mediterranea of Reggio Calabria, Italy and CNIT, Italy

[‡]Dept. DIMES, University of Calabria, Italy and CNIT, Italy

{*dspatharakis,jdimol,gztzanettis,nfilinis,efotopoulou,cvassilakis*}@netmode.ntua.gr, *tzafeir@cn.ntua.gr*
{*giacomo.genovese, antonella.molinaro*}@unirc.it, *antonio.iera@dimes.unical.it, papavass@mail.ntua.gr*

Abstract—With the rapid advancement in the next-generation Internet of Things (IoT) and the ever-expanding virtual representation of devices, novel techniques and definitions are key to accommodate emerging paradigms to transform our world. In the quest of achieving the coveted convergence of IoT technologies with the Cloud-Edge computing continuum and the seamless interaction of IoT devices and hyper-distributed applications, we enhance the concept of Virtual Objects (VOs) for the virtualization of IoT devices in the wake of recent works. We introduce a software stack, called VOSTack, to enable interoperability and convergence between the physical IoT devices layer and the Edge/Cloud virtualized infrastructure. The VOSTack tackles interoperability with IoT devices and provides a unified way for their control, enables smooth lifecycle management of the VOs, and allows the development of modern distributed applications by offering on-demand capabilities to support IoT application operations. The necessary interactions of the VOs are presented along with the essential core functionalities for the development of the VOSTack. Finally, an overview of different deployment models aligned with the state of practice of infrastructure providers is detailed.

Index Terms—Virtual Object, Digital Twin, Computing Continuum, IoT Application, IoT Interoperability

I. INTRODUCTION

The next generation of Internet of Things (IoT), edge and cloud computing technologies are evolving at a rapid pace and are transforming businesses and peoples' lives, producing solutions targeted at many industrial sectors, and forming the foundation of a totally interconnected world [1]. This evolution moves in parallel with the increase in the heterogeneity of the IoT technologies [2] in terms of the production of different types of intelligent IoT devices, the support of diverse communication protocols, and the conceptualization of various information models for semantically representing entities in the IoT world. These trends drive the need for novel architectural approaches, that support by design the full convergence and integration between existing and evolving IoT, edge and cloud computing technologies.

In parallel, data processing and machine learning workflows are foreseen to rapidly shift towards edge computing facilities [3]. To efficiently handle data management and

analytics in such a distributed environment, novel applications are increasingly embracing microservices-based and cloud-native computing technologies, while distributed computing principles are deeply evolving their lifecycle orchestration paradigms to efficiently leverage resources in the computing continuum from the IoT to the edge to the cloud [4].

Two main challenges arise in this transition. The first challenge regards the need for convergence of IoT technologies based on novel architectural approaches, able to guarantee openness and seamless interoperability of the plethora of existing and emerging solutions, models and devices. The second challenge regards the integration of IoT technologies with edge and cloud computing technologies, offering transparent deployment and orchestration solutions for IoT applications across the computing continuum.

To tackle these challenges in a device-independent way, we introduce an IoT and edge computing software stack leveraging the virtualization of IoT devices at the edge of the infrastructure. The proposed stack addresses IoT interoperability and openness aspects at two different levels, namely (i) the IoT device level, based on the provision of virtual counterparts of IoT devices, and (ii) the level of integration of IoT functions with edge and cloud computing applications.

At the first level, the concept of Virtual Object (VO) is introduced. The VO is considered as the virtual counterpart of an IoT device that significantly extends the concept of Digital Twin. It, in fact, provides a set of abstractions for managing any type of IoT device through a virtualized instance while augmenting the supported functionalities through the hosting of a multi-layer software stack, called Virtual Object Stack (VOSTack). The VOSTack is specifically conceived to provide VOs with edge and IoT computing functionality. As for the second level, by jointly exploiting the VOSTack and the microservice paradigm, we empower the design of distributed applications where the IoT, edge, and cloud computing applications' components can be jointly represented in a single application graph (i.e., a set of applications components mutually linked). The IoT application components can be

represented in the form of functions supported by the VO, while the edge and cloud computing application parts can be represented as pure edge/cloud-native functions.

II. IOT DEVICES VIRTUALIZATION AND MOTIVATION

The Virtual Object (VO) as a digital counterpart of a physical IoT device has experienced an evolution of its functionality over the years. Since its introduction, in most of its deployments, the VO concept has been commonly intended to promote the interoperability of heterogeneous devices, facilitate the deployment of new services, improve reachability, and achieve self-management of devices [5]. Several other features further enhanced the VO as part of a variety of fit-for-purpose introduced management frameworks: common semantic representation of the device's data and functionalities for enhanced interoperability, device augmentation with compute and storage capabilities, device augmentation with context awareness and cognitive management, device offloading and energy consumption optimization, are just a few examples.

As a further step, a more effective collaboration of several physical devices is enabled in the virtual world by the introduction of the Composite Virtual Object (cVO) as an aggregation of trusted VOs illustrating a new set of functions out of the interaction of several member devices through their virtual counterparts. Deployments presented so far do not always consider a single corresponding VO to a physical device but have also introduced solutions, adapted to their reference scenario, where a single VO may correspond to multiple physical devices, each of them performing different functions/services, or multiple VOs correspond to a single physical device [6]. Furthermore, the combination of several VOs and cVOs along with other services, results into a new higher level of IoT services and applications, while their orchestration and execution in the cloud and/or edge have triggered the introduction of several methods and frameworks often targeted to a specific application area [7].

The concept of Digital twin (DT) also bases its definition on the mapping of a physical object onto a virtual space and builds upon it to illustrate a synchronous bidirectional data exchange to monitor, simulate, predict, diagnose, and control the state and behavior of the physical object within the virtual space [8]. One could think of a DT as a VO or cVO with a set of advanced features and tight synchronicity and state matching with the physical object. It is believed that an open VO design establishing it as a potential building block of a DT or even future cyber-physical systems would promote significant advances in the area.

Emergent applications developed in a cloud-native/microservices-based fashion, as service chains of scalable components-microservices, leverage a hyper-distributed execution of their interconnected components over a computing continuum of orchestrated resources in different network domains (IoT, edge, cloud) [9]. In light of these new requirements and potential, the VO design should be revisited to set the VO as a facilitator for: (i) a unified

devices management, overcoming interoperability issues; (ii) the development of computing continuum native IoT applications where convergence aspects with edge and cloud computing technologies are tackled; and (iii) the development of new cyber-physical paradigms and new IoT-driven business models.

To facilitate the development and efficient orchestration of new emergent applications, we argue that the VO/cVO should be part of the application graph having itself a cloud-native nature. We consider a single correspondent VO per physical device while we expand the definition of cVO not only to be able to illustrate the collaboration of several VOs but also to be able to augment and personalize a single VO. This approach provides the required flexibility to efficiently illustrate new IoT-driven business models and address diverse application areas. We also introduce a multi-layered lightweight software stack (named VOStack) for leveraging the virtualization of IoT devices at the edge part of the infrastructure and supporting openness and interoperability aspects in a device-independent way.

III. VIRTUAL OBJECT SPECIFICATION

In the following Sections, we describe the envisioned approach to the VO development and the convergence aspects with the computing continuum. The proposed VO is expected to provide an adequate set of interaction capabilities, both with physical IoT devices and with edge/cloud computing management mechanisms, in the various operating environments of the application and the computing orchestration platforms. Therefore, it is important to clearly define the VO, as well as the rest of the key elements that the latter interacts within the computing continuum. Prior to delving into details for the VO specification, we provide a set of definitions that we consider helpful for a better understanding of the considered terms. These terms regard the IoT Device, the IoT Gateway, the IoT Device Cluster, the Digital Twin and the Client of a VO.

A. IoT Terms Definition

With the term **IoT Device** we refer to a device with one or more sensors, computational capabilities (optional) and a communication interface. The IoT Device can act as a sensor (produces data based on the observations by sensors) and/or an actuator (applies/enforces actions).

In various cases, to achieve network connectivity and enable management capabilities for IoT devices, the use of a smart IoT gateway is necessary. With the term **IoT Gateway**, we refer to a device that is used as an aggregation point in the IoT domain, connecting various on-the-ground devices with an edge Point of Presence (PoP). The IoT Gateway may support different communication protocols for interacting with the IoT devices. To represent cases where a set of identical IoT devices create clusters and operate in a given area (e.g., a set of humidity sensors that monitors humidity in a smart agriculture scenario), we use the term **Cluster Manager** which is a software component whose objective is to allow many

similar devices to be managed as a single IoT Device, this meaning that the state and actions of the Manager refer to all the devices in the cluster at the same time.

A **Digital Twin (DT)** is a virtual representation of a real-world physical system or product (a physical twin) that serves as the indistinguishable digital counterpart of it for practical purposes, such as system simulation, integration, testing, monitoring, and maintenance. A DT can but has not necessarily to be used in real-time and regularly synchronized with the corresponding physical system.

From the perspective of the edge/cloud application or service providers that aim to deploy applications based on IoT-related data and actions, the VO has to be considered as a part of their application's graph. To represent this interaction, we introduce the term **VO Client**. The VO Client is considered as an application component that requests data or dictates actions to the IoT Device represented by its VO.

Given the aforementioned definitions regarding IoT-related concepts, we proceed by defining the proposed VO in III-B and the associated software stack (VOStack) in III-C.

B. Virtual Object Definition

A **Virtual Object (VO)** is considered as a virtual counterpart of a physical device on the Internet of Things domain. It provides a set of abstractions for managing any type of IoT device through a virtualized instance while augmenting the supported functionalities through the development of a multi-layer software stack, called Virtual Object Stack (VOStack) (see Section III-C).

The relationship between a VO and an IoT device is one-to-one. To meet the strict requirements of the IoT-specific scenarios, the VO is intended to be deployed in small-scale data-centers at the network edge, in the proximity of the corresponding IoT device. The integration of the appropriate communication protocols within the VO is essential to ensure efficient interactions with the device layer. From the client's perspective, the VO is considered part of an application graph, providing application-related functionalities (e.g., accessing the IoT data or enforcing actions on IoT devices). The VO is orchestratable as part of the application graph and, thus, can be managed, monitored, scaled, and migrated.

As the proposed VO is intended to operate in close proximity to its hardware counterpart, the resource constraints of small-scale infrastructures at the network edge must be accounted for in view to matching the VO's requirements. On the other hand, various application scenarios might demand computing-intensive tasks to be scheduled or data from different IoT devices to be aggregated for further processing. In such cases, the custom, application-specific configuration is necessary per client and the basic VO capabilities must be enhanced. In order to keep the VO isolated and as lightweight as possible while, at the same time, allowing clients to deploy custom functionalities in the IoT device proximity, or combine data from different IoT devices, which will be part of the application graph and fully configurable by the clients, we introduce the concept of Composite VO.

Fig. 1: High-level view for the VO positioning in the computing continuum.

A **Composite Virtual Object (cVO)** is a software entity that is able to manage the information coming from one or multiple VOs and provide advanced functionalities. Two modes of operation are designed for a cVO. In the first mode, a cVO is connected with multiple VOs that manage IoT devices of several types. The cVO interacts with the VOs, processes the collected information, and is able to contextually produce advanced knowledge, by enabling the communication and collaboration of several VOs, toward the production and exposure of a combined set of data outputs.

Thus, a cVO can be used as an aggregation entity of multiple VOs of various types to provide clients' applications with a single point of access to the information of multiple IoT devices. As a result, it is part of an application graph undertaking the role of a VO Client, while the relationship between a cVO and multiple VOs is one-to-many. The cVO can guide the behaviour of the managed VOs by enforcing kind of policies for their optimal collaboration (e.g., synchronization in data acquisition processes). In the second mode, the cVO enhances the capabilities of the VO through the provision of application-oriented functionalities, once again under the role of a VO client. For instance, in case of a video camera, the cVO can support image recognition features over the streams managed by the VO. Under the scope of this mode, the cVO can operate also as a DT. In this case, the enhanced capabilities of the VO through the cVO refer to the support of simulation, integration, testing, monitoring and maintenance activities for an IoT device.

Figure 1 provides a high-level convergence view across the computing continuum, wherein the proposed VO is able to communicate with IoT devices, thus enabling their interconnection with application-oriented parts (application

graphs). In particular, representative cases of IoT devices managed by VOs are illustrated. For example, complex IoT devices with multiple sensors, such as a robotic arm, could be virtually represented by a VO, while a cVO might extend the device’s functionalities and capabilities with regard to the application’s requirements or operate as a DT for the robotic arm. Furthermore, leveraging the capabilities of the Cluster Manager, the VO could manage a cluster of identical IoT devices. The data produced from different IoT devices (such as a camera and a temperature sensor), could be aggregated and processed by a cVO, in accordance with the application’s objective. As it is also shown, a VO could provide the retrieved data from the corresponding IoT device to several application-oriented components of the same or distinct service graphs.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, to support all the envisioned capabilities, a VO has the following main types of interactions with the computing continuum world:

VO-to-IoT-Device Interaction: the objective is to solve interoperability and convergence challenges with the IoT ecosystem.

VO-to-Application Interaction: the objective is to enable the interaction between the VO and cVOs, as well as the interaction between the (c)VO and application components that provide part of the distributed application business logic.

VO-to-Orchestration Interaction: the objective is to enable the development of edge/cloud computing distributed applications, where the (c)VO is an integral part of a distributed application graph and, thus, manageable by cloud/edge computing orchestration mechanisms.

VO-to-Storage Entity Interaction: the objective is to keep track of device metadata, status and messages exchanged with other devices and applications. Moreover, the VO must be able to support basic operations regarding data management by integrating multiple data sources to produce contextual information about the devices that can be used by the clients.

C. Virtual Object Software Stack

A software stack (VOStack) is under development to flexibly support interaction with both physical IoT devices and edge/cloud computing orchestration platforms, considering both the VO and cVO concept. The VOSTack is implemented in the context of stateless pluggable micro-services. The main incentive is that the VOs must be lightweight and modular while supporting basic functionalities that most devices and applications need. Hence, the VOSTack has three main architectural layers namely: (i) the Physical Convergence Layer, (ii) the Edge/Cloud Convergence Layer, and (iii) the Backend Logic Layer. Following, we analyze them along with the functionality envisaged per layer. In Fig. 3 we present an overview of the layered approach of the VOSTack.

1) *Physical Convergence Layer:* This layer is responsible to tackle the major challenges of connecting the IoT devices with the computing continuum infrastructure. First and foremost, the VO is able to address device registration issues (e.g., registering a new device to a VO, bootstrapping of a connection, etc.). Regarding protocol interoperability, a VO

Fig. 2: The interactions of the VO with the Computing Continuum ecosystem.

supports different types of communication protocols among those most widely used in the IoT domain at: (i) the application layer (e.g., MQTT, CoAP, HTTP, etc.), (ii) the network layer (e.g., IPv4, IPv6, etc.), and (iii) transport layer (e.g., TCP, UDP, etc.). In such a way, the majority of IoT devices are able to be connected and communicate with their virtual counterpart. However, as many devices have restricted security capabilities, authentication and authorization functionalities (e.g., OAuth 2.0) are provided to solve secure communications between the devices and the applications. Moreover, this layer simplifies the coordination of multiple IoT devices or IoT clusters, by providing autonomic and self-* functionalities [10]. Furthermore, a set of network-oriented functionalities are available to facilitate intermittent connectivity of the devices, manage dynamic routing protocols, time-sensitive networking mechanisms or tackle mobility aspects. On the one hand, by keeping the VO synced with the IoT device, clients are able to access the device’s information uninterruptedly even if the device suddenly loses connection with the VO.

2) *Backend Logic Layer:* This layer is responsible for augmenting the functionalities and capabilities of IoT devices. Here, we include all the logic related to the IoT device’s operational behaviors, enhanced functionalities, and services that the Object/Device can perform. Primarily, the VOs are able to declare alerts on the IoT devices’ state (e.g., a device suddenly restarted), and/or data-driven notifications (e.g., the temperature of a sensor rapidly increased). This functionality is closely related to the interaction with the storage entity, since, for instance, it is typical in many scenarios to observe past data values. Naturally, in trying to implement the virtual counterpart of an IoT device it is mandatory to introduce a set of actions and behaviors that the VO can dictate to the IoT device. To this extent, a VO can reconfigure or try to remotely heal a device. Moreover, following an event-based logic,

Fig. 3: VOSTack layers.

actions are also either triggered by the monitored data (e.g., alerts and notifications coming from a sensor) or activated by commands received from the application and/or orchestration side (e.g., an application provider may want to dictate a different behavior of a sensor, such as changing the polling period of measurement when a given threshold is exceeded). Finally, for each defined action, a mechanism is designed to support the action-related policies implementing multi-tenancy characteristics. It is crucial that the set of actions, alerts, and notifications are reconfigurable and their definitions are not limited or heavily depend on the respective use case. Moreover, the modularity of IoT functions in the edge and the cloud infrastructure is considered a key challenge to enabling modern applications and cloud-native IoT solutions. To this end, two main categories of functionalities are defined to support the basic operations that the interplay between IoT and Applications require, namely (i) IoT Device Virtualized Functions and (ii) Generic/Supportive Functions.

The IoT Device Virtualized Functions refer to functions that tackle part of the business logic of an application. They are responsible for the deployment and management of IoT-specific functionalities (e.g., video transcoding for a camera, image processing and analysis in case of a remote healthcare device or a face detection sensor). The objective is to alleviate IoT devices from executing computationally heavy tasks and transfer this responsibility to the VOs that are deployed in a nearby edge computing infrastructure. Virtualization of IoT functions enables their integration into edge computing applications and their dynamic management by edge and cloud computing orchestration platforms. The IoT Device Virtualized Functions are mostly envisaged to be provided in the form of cVOs, as an advanced capability of a VO.

The Generic/Supportive Functions consider a set of supportive functions that can be horizontally applied

over all the instantiated VOs for an application. These functions can support IoT-oriented functionalities in a generic way (e.g., distributed data management, data aggregation, filtering, firewalling, authentication, failure handling), as well as functionalities at the edge part of the infrastructure (e.g., service discovery, telemetry). As a result, the Generic/Supportive VO functions should be part of the basic VO implementation and may be activated on demand according to the application's needs.

3) *Edge/Cloud Convergence Layer*: This layer is responsible for bringing the VO closer to the application and orchestration layer. As the VO is part of the application graph, it communicates with entities, such as data consumers, applications, or users, through suitable interfaces. Various communication protocols (e.g., HTTP, MQTT, etc.) and semantic/standardization protocols (e.g. OMA LwM2M [11], NGSI-LD [12], Web of Things [13]) are going to be supported. Hence, via this layer, IoT devices are exposed and consumed. More specifically, a set of functionalities may be provided through this layer for managing incoming requests and providing responses (e.g., requesting data, triggering actions, declaring new alerts), and handling multi-tenancy aspects (e.g., multiple requests for IoT device information). Besides, this layer supports a set of functions related to orchestration and addressing the monitoring of the status of the VO (e.g., container monitoring), the management of the deployment of the VO over the computing infrastructure (e.g., start, stop, restart, destroy), and the management of elasticity and migration actions.

IV. VIRTUAL OBJECT DEPLOYMENT MODELS

In this section, we provide an overview of the deployment models that we consider dominant for distributed IoT applications that adopt the proposed approach. We consider stakeholders such as IoT Device Providers, Infrastructure Providers, VO and cVO operators and edge or cloud computing Application Providers. Depending on the owners of the infrastructure, these roles in some cases may be overlapping. In Fig. 4 we present the following scenarios.

Let's consider the scenario where the VO is managed by the Infrastructure Provider. In this case, we consider that the IoT devices belong to a Device Provider and can be connected to an infrastructure. The infrastructure is programmable, and the Infrastructure Provider is responsible to deploy/instantiate the VOs over computing resources, usually in the (far) edge part of the infrastructure. Upon instantiation, the VO can be made available to multiple tenants (Application Providers) for data consumption and (if possible) for enforcement of actions to the IoT device.

Starting from the VO, cVOs can be created, managed by the Infrastructure Provider, and made available to the associated tenant (Application Provider). Alternatively, the cVOs can be managed by the Application Provider in a similar way that it manages the remaining application components. To facilitate the selection and usage of (c)VOs, the existence of a (c)VO repository is envisaged. Depending on the deployment model,

different stakeholders may have different access rights to the repository. An important aspect here is to decide how to implement the method of exploiting the data of the various VOs by different tenants to feed their different applications (multi-tenancy approach). The cVO could be used to maintain the separation of roles, to adhere to the basic principle that a single VO is associated one-to-one with the IoT device counterpart, and, at the same time, to be able to describe the same IoT device through different virtualized images (different views of the VO) for the different tenants that use it. In fact, the same VO could be associated with a set of cVOs, each of which could offer a different view of the same VO through a many-to-one correspondence (many cVOs associated with a single VO in turn associated with the IoT device).

The (c)VO repository can be used to provide various cVO models, made available to the various tenants. This makes it possible to offer views of the VOs controlled by the Infrastructure Provider and to guarantee a greater isolation between device data and tenant applications. In this case, for some VOs a set of views would be offered that the tenant can choose when negotiating with the Infrastructure Provider.

In an alternative scenario, it is considered that a third-party (c)VO Operator exists between the Infrastructure Provider and the Application Provider. Compared to the previous case, the (c)VO Operator, following business agreements, will manage the (c)VOs lifecycle on the infrastructure of the Infrastructure Provider. The users' IoT devices will be registered directly on the third-party platform and the (c)VOs will be managed within it. In this case, the tenants will interface with the (c)VO Operator which will offer the tenant applications the set of devices registered to the platform through their virtual images (VOs and cVOs). With a view to interoperability, it could take charge of interfacing its VOs with VOs defined by other platforms so that its virtualized devices can be made available in platforms that use different standardized interfaces (e.g., W3C) towards applications and which are already operating on infrastructures of Infrastructure Providers with which it intends to enter into a business agreement.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents the concept of VOs and VOSTack and addresses all the necessary aspects for the seamless interaction between IoT technologies and the computing continuum. An IoT ecosystem is defined that leverages the paradigm of VOs as virtual counterparts of IoT devices. The interactions of the VOs with entities of the computing continuum are described, the core functionalities of the VOSTack are presented, and details on how we envisage to design the VOSTack as an open-source stack for IoT applications development are provided. This work paves the way for the seamless integration of virtualized IoT devices with the Edge/Cloud ecosystem and for the design and deployment of modern distributed applications. As a future work, we aim to integrate the VO with a synergistic orchestration framework for managing hyper-distributed applications over the computing continuum.

Fig. 4: Deployment scenarios and interactions

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070487.

REFERENCES

- [1] 5G Americas white paper, "5G: The Future of IoT," 2019.
- [2] J.-M. Fernandez, I. Vidal, and F. Valera, "Enabling the orchestration of iot slices through edge and cloud microservice platforms," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 13, 2019.
- [3] Z. Zhong, M. Xu, M. A. Rodriguez, C. Xu, and R. Buyya, "Machine learning-based orchestration of containers: A taxonomy and future directions," *ACM Comput. Surv.*, jan 2022.
- [4] D. Kimovski, R. Mathá, J. Hammer, N. Mehran, H. Hellwagner, and R. Prodan, "Cloud, fog, or edge: Where to compute?," *IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 30–36, 2021.
- [5] M. Nitti, V. Pilloni, G. Colistra, and L. Atzori, "The virtual object as a major element of the internet of things: A survey," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 18, pp. 1228–1240, 2016.
- [6] L. Atzori, J. L. Bellido, R. Bolla, G. Genovese, A. Iera, A. J. Jara, C. Lombardo, and G. Morabito, "Sdn&nfv contribution to iot objects virtualization," *Comput. Networks*, vol. 149, pp. 200–212, 2019.
- [7] M. A. Jarwar, S. Ali, and I. Chong, "A microservices model to enhance the availability of data for building energy efficiency management services," *Energies*, 2019.
- [8] M. Segovia and J. García, "Design, modeling and implementation of digital twins," *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 22, 2022.
- [9] H. Kokkonen, L. Lovén, N. H. Motlagh, J. Partala, A. Gonz'alez-Gil, E. Sola, I. Angulo, M. Liyanage, T. Leppanen, T. Nguyen, P. Kostakos, M. Bennis, S. Tarkoma, S. Dustdar, S. Pirttikangas, and J. Riekkki, "Autonomy and intelligence in the computing continuum: Challenges, enablers, and future directions for orchestration," *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2205.01423, 2022.
- [10] M. Sánchez, E. Exposito, and J. Aguilar, "Implementing self-* autonomic properties in self-coordinated manufacturing processes for the industry 4.0 context," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 121, p. 103247, 2020.
- [11] Open Mobile Alliance, "Internet of Things Protocol Comparison," 2018.
- [12] G. Privat, "Guidelines for modelling with ngsi-ld," *ETSI White Paper*, no. 42, 2021.
- [13] M. Lagally and M. McCool, "Iot interoperability with w3c web of things," in *2022 IEEE 19th Annual Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC)*, pp. 1–5, 2022.